

Launch Power Control for Digital Subcarrier Equalization in Filterless Optical Networks

Mohammad M. Hosseini
Infinera, Munich
Germany
MHosseini@infinera.com

João Pedro
Infinera Unipessoal, Lda
Carnaxide, Portugal
Instituto de Telecomunicações, IST
Lisboa, Portugal
JPedro@infinera.com

Antonio Napoli
Infinera, Munich
Germany
ANapoli@infinera.com

Abstract—This paper investigates the advantages of exploiting launch power control in point-to-multipoint (P2MP) transceivers when deployed in filterless horseshoe optical networks. In order to realize simple and cost-effective optical nodes, 2-by-2 optical couplers can be used in these networks, resulting in a filterless architecture that avoids the deployment of expensive wavelength selective switches (WSSs). Optical amplifiers can be deployed as needed to compensate for losses. However, if P2MP transceivers are used, in the upstream direction the receiver can only tolerate up to a certain difference between the power levels of the incoming signals. Meeting this limit may demand additional amplifiers to be used in the transmission paths. Leveraging the ability to control the launch power of each transmitter in the upstream direction can mitigate the need to deploy additional amplifiers. This work proposes a mathematical framework to minimize the number of optical amplifiers required in filterless horseshoe networks fitted with P2MP transceivers with launch power control. The results support the benefits of having launch power control in the transceivers to reduce the number of optical amplifiers required when exploiting P2MP connectivity in the optical domain.

Index Terms—optical power control, point-to-multipoint, filterless architecture, network optimization.

I. INTRODUCTION

High-bandwidth, flexible, reliable, and cost-effective communication is crucial for metro-aggregation networks. Horseshoe and ring topologies are common choices in this network segment [1], [2]. Digital subcarrier coherent multiplexing (DSCM) is enabling a new generation of point-to-multipoint (P2MP) transceivers [3]. These P2MP transceivers offer a cost-effective way to handle the hub-and-spoke traffic patterns typical of metro-aggregation networks. By combining multiple smaller data rates into a single high-bandwidth signal at hub locations, P2MP transceivers can significantly reduce costs, power consumption, and space requirements compared to conventional point-to-point (P2P) solutions.

Traditional optical networks rely on expensive and power-hungry equipment to manage data flows. Filterless optical networks offer a simpler, more efficient alternative. Unlike

traditional Wavelength Division Multiplexing (WDM) networks using active and complex WSSs, filterless networks use simple passive splitters and combiners. This filterless approach perfectly complements DSCM-based P2MP transceivers. Together, they reduce the need for expensive, power-hungry electronics, leading to significant cost savings, lower power consumption, and a simpler network management [4], [5].

While filterless networks offer advantages, their lack of filtering leads to bandwidth waste. Due to the lack of filters, each light tree occupies a channel across all optical links but only accommodates one source-destination pair. Therefore, the optical bandwidth of the entire network will be simply equal to a single fiber for pure filterless networks (only light-tree). P2MP transceivers can reduce the bandwidth waste via fine-grained (i.e., sub-wavelength) optical aggregation. Note that for access and metro-aggregation networks, the available optical spectrum is usually much larger than the capacity demands present in these segments. Additionally, fixed filters can be used in situations where deployed capacity approaches available bandwidth (typically the C-band).

A challenge for DSCM-based P2MP transmission is that unequal power levels arise in upstream signals because each leaf node transceiver takes a unique path with varying loss and gain characteristics. These imbalanced power levels in upstream subcarriers (SCs) create a problem: low-power SCs can only utilize a portion of their analog-to-digital converter's (ADC) available quantization levels. This effectively reduces the usable resolution and the effective number of bits (ENOB) of the ADCs. Consequently, the signal-to-noise ratio (OSNR) can be impacted, potentially leading to substantial and unacceptable packet loss (see [6]–[8] for more details).

Launch power is a critical factor in optical transmission systems, directly impacting signal quality at the receiver. While intuitively increasing launch power might seem beneficial, it is limited by both non-linear effects within the fiber and technological constraints. For example, pluggable coherent transceivers often have a maximum launch power restricted by size and power consumption limitations. Research in [9] explored optimizing launch power allocation alongside other factors in the non-linear regime. Their work aimed to improve network resource utilization and boost overall throughput. In

ultra-wide-band systems spanning the C+L bands, managing fiber input power becomes even more crucial. This is due to various optical phenomena like stimulated Raman scattering, which can significantly degrade system performance, as highlighted in [10]. Nevertheless, the potential of the launch power control feature has been less exploited in metro-aggregation network scenarios. Our prior research explored the potential of using various optical coupler ratios to leverage their inherent flexibility [1], [11]. We demonstrated how this approach could reduce the number of amplifiers needed and minimize the power difference between SCs at the hub receiver. However, these works did not consider the additional degrees of flexibility offered by adjusting the launch power of the P2MP transceivers themselves. In this paper, we address this gap by investigating and quantifying the benefits of power control for P2MP transceivers within filterless horseshoe networks.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section II provides a short overview of the network architecture and how horseshoe topologies are modeled. Section III delves into the specifics of the optimization framework customized for this work. Finally, section IV presents the study's findings and discusses the key observations, whereas section V presents the concluding remarks.

II. NETWORK ARCHITECTURE

The metro-aggregation network is assumed to comprise a horseshoe topology, as depicted in Fig. 1. This design provides redundancy in case of hub or link failures. The network employs filterless nodes constructed using 2-by-2 couplers and incorporates optical amplifiers for signal strength, which can be selectively deployed to reduce the total infrastructure cost. The couplers in leaf sites can be balanced or unbalanced allowing unequal distribution of power for express or add/drop ports. Optical amplifiers can be placed just before leaf nodes in each fiber direction, as in-line amplifiers, and as booster pre-amplifiers at hub sites. While the design utilizes two transceivers per leaf node, the architecture can be scaled to deploy more transceivers per site if needed. This scenario is not considered here for simplicity, but the core design strategy can be easily modified to consider these cases. In this paper, we consider an 8-leaf node horseshoe topology. Therefore, a maximum of 16 in-line amplifiers and 4 booster and pre-amplifiers can be deployed. However, the goal is to minimize the number of amplifiers using an exact optimization framework that will be described in the following section.

We investigated link lengths in metro-aggregation networks operated by Telecom Italia Mobile. Our goal was to find a statistical model to generate realistic link lengths for network designs. We analyzed data from 495 links across 13 networks (each a combination of horseshoe or horseshoe-and-spur topologies). The log-normal distribution [12] was shown to provide the best fit, with a mean link length of 12 km and a standard deviation of 11.3 km, as presented in Fig. 2. This distribution will serve as the baseline for the rest of the paper. Additionally, we introduce a second log-normal distribution, named the "extended distribution," to represent longer links in

larger horseshoes. This extended distribution has a mean of 24 km and a standard deviation of 15.8 km.

Digital signal processing (DSP) constitutes the key differentiation between DSCM transceivers and single-carrier P2P coherent transceivers. While their optical components exhibit significant similarity, DSCM transceivers leverage parallel processing capabilities within the DSP [3]. Current standardization efforts advocate for the use of 25 Gbps SCs with 16-quadrature amplitude modulation (16-QAM) for P2MP applications [13]. This configuration operates at a symbol rate of 4 GBaud. It is noteworthy that alternative modulation formats can be employed, influencing the capacity achievable per SC. For instance, a 400 Gbps transceiver would necessitate the utilization of 16 SCs, leading to a total symbol rate of approximately 64 Gbaud. This configuration facilitates communication with either four leaf nodes, each receiving 100 Gbps, or up to 16 leaf nodes, each receiving 25 Gbps.

III. OPTIMIZATION FRAMEWORK

The optimization framework devised and implemented in the scope of this work intends to provide a low-cost and power-budget feasible solution. Two main objectives are embedded in the proposed optimization framework for filterless horseshoe networks featuring P2MP transceivers:

- Minimize the total number of amplifiers: the total number of amplifiers includes express and booster/pre-amplifiers. The cost of amplifiers is proportional to this metric.
- Minimize the maximum SC power difference: this is one of the main DSCM-based P2MP transceiver metrics to ensure high-performance operation.

The framework described in this section is a modified version of the one based on integer linear programming (ILP) originally proposed in [1]. The modifications enable us to consider both fiber transmission directions and select the per transceiver optimal launch power from a given range. Additionally, the framework incorporates booster/pre-amplifiers for hub nodes and passive 2-by-2 couplers. In the following, we present the model's main decision variables and input parameters (Table. I).

Decision Variables

- $\Delta_{l,t}^s$: Binary variable for coupler selection; 1 if coupler s is selected for leaf l at direction t , 0 otherwise.
- $\gamma_{l,t}^p$: Loss of port p of coupler in leaf l in direction t .
- $\mu_{a,g}^{12}$: Binary variable; 1 if express amplifier on link a takes gain g for fiber direction Hub1 to Hub2.
- $\mu_{a,g}^{21}$: Binary variable; 1 if the amplifier at the link a takes the gain g for the fiber direction Hub2 to Hub1.
- μ_g^{b1} / μ_g^{b2} : Binary variables; 1 if the booster amplifier at Hub1/Hub2 l takes the gain g , otherwise 0.
- μ_g^{p1} / μ_g^{p2} : Binary variable; 1 if the pre-amplifier at Hub1/Hub2 l takes the gain g , otherwise 0.
- $p_{l,t,z}^{leaf}$: Binary variables; 1 if transceiver located at leaf l in direction t takes launch power z .

Fig. 1. Horseshoe filterless topology, amplifiers placement options, and the employed node architecture.

TABLE I
INPUT PARAMETERS

Symbol	Description
L	List of leaf nodes
A	List of fiber links loss
G_g	Set of EDFA gains, 0 implies no amplifier
P_z	Set of launch power values
$M_{d,u}^{l,a}$	Binary link-path matrix ($ L \times A $) from Hub1 to leaf nodes; 1 if path from Hub1 to leaf l contains link a
$M_{u,d}^{l,a}$	Binary link-path matrix ($ L \times A $) from leaf nodes to Hub2; 1 if path from leaf l to Hub 2 contains link a
$N_{d,u}^{l,lx}$	Binary node-path matrix ($ L \times L $) from Hub1 to leaf nodes; 1 if path from Hub1 to leaf l passes leaf lx
$N_{u,d}^{l,lx}$	Binary node-path matrix ($ L \times L $) from leaf nodes to Hub2; 1 if path from leaf l to Hub2 passes leaf lx
P_n	Nonlinearity power threshold per SC
P_s	Sensitivity power level
P_x	SCs maximum power difference tolerance
H_s^p	Add/drop and express losses of coupler s

Fig. 2. Probability Density Functions (PDFs) of Log-normal distribution fitted to empirical link data using Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE) and an extended horseshoe distribution.

- $p_{t,z}^{hub}$: Binary variables; 1 if transceiver located at Hub transmitting in t direction takes launch power z .
- ϕ_l^{12d} : Leaf l Rx power per SC coming from Hub1.
- ϕ_l^{12u} : Hub2 Rx power per SC coming from leaf l .
- ϕ_l^{21d} : Leaf l Rx power per SC coming from Hub2.
- ϕ_l^{21u} : Hub1 Rx power per SC coming from the leaf l .
- $\epsilon_{11}, \epsilon_{12}$: Lower and upper bounds of variables ϕ_l^{12u} .
- $\epsilon_{21}, \epsilon_{22}$: Lower and upper bounds of variables ϕ_l^{21u} .

Equation (1) presents the objective function of the ILP model and consists of three terms: the first two express

the number of amplifiers, whereas the second expresses the maximum SC power difference.

$$z = \sum_{a,g \neq 1} (\mu_{a,g}^{12} + \mu_{a,g}^{21}) G_g + \sum_{l,g \neq 1} (\mu_g^{p1} + \mu_g^{p2} + \mu_g^{b1} + \mu_g^{b2}) G_g + w[\epsilon_{12} - \epsilon_{11} + \epsilon_{22} - \epsilon_{21}] \quad (1)$$

where w is a weighting factor that controls the priority of the last objective compared to the first one.

$$\sum_g \mu_{XX}^{YY} = 1, \quad \forall a \in A \text{ or } l \in L \quad (2)$$

Constraints (2) select an index for the gain of all amplifiers in the network (XX and YY have to be replaced with appropriate indices for each set of amplifiers).

$$\sum_s \Delta_{l,t}^s = 1 \quad \forall l \in L, t \in \{12, 21\} \quad (3)$$

$$\gamma_{l,t}^p = \sum_s \Delta_{l,t}^s \times H_s^p \quad \forall l, t, p \in \{add/drop, exp\} \quad (4)$$

Constraints (3) are used to choose the couplers types at each leaf node. Accordingly, constraints (4) assign the resulting loss to each port of the couplers.

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_l^{12d} = & -\gamma_{l,12}^{add/drop} - \sum_a A_a M_d^{l,a} - \sum_{lx} \gamma_{lx,12}^{exp} N_d^{l,lx} + \\ & \sum_z p_{12,z}^{hub} P_z + \sum_g (\mu_{l,g}^{d_1} + \mu_g^{b_1}) G_g + \sum_a \sum_g \mu_{a,g}^{12} G_g M_d^{l,a} \\ & \forall l \in L \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_l^{12u} = & -\gamma_{l,12}^{add/drop} - \sum_a A_a M_u^{l,a} - \sum_{lx} \gamma_{lx,12}^{exp} N_u^{l,lx} + \\ & \sum_z p_{l,12,z}^{leaf} P_z + \sum_g (\mu_{l,g}^{u_1} + \mu_g^{p_2}) G_g + \sum_a \sum_g \mu_{a,g}^{12} G_g M_u^{l,a} \\ & \forall l \in L \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_l^{21d} = & -\gamma_{l,21}^{add/drop} - \sum_a A_a M_u^{l,a} - \sum_{lx} \gamma_{lx,21}^{exp} N_u^{l,lx} + \\ & \sum_z p_{21,z}^{hub} P_z + \sum_g (\mu_{l,g}^{d_2} + \mu_g^{b_2}) G_g + \sum_a \sum_g \mu_{a,g}^{21} G_g M_u^{l,a} \\ & \forall l \in L \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_l^{21u} = & -\gamma_{l,21}^{add/drop} - \sum_a A_a M_d^{l,a} - \sum_{lx} \gamma_{lx,21}^{exp} N_d^{l,lx} + \\ & \sum_z p_{l,21,z}^{leaf} P_z + \sum_g (\mu_{l,g}^{u_2} + \mu_g^{p_1}) G_g + \sum_a \sum_g \mu_{a,g}^{21} G_g M_d^{l,a} \\ & \forall l \in L \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Constraints (5) to (8) calculate the power level received at the transceivers located at hub and leaf nodes.

$$\phi_l^{XX} \geq P_s, \quad \forall l \in L, \quad (9)$$

The series of constraints listed in (9) ensure that the received power level is greater than the transceiver's sensitivity.

$$\epsilon_{11} \geq \phi_l^{12u}, \quad \epsilon_{12} \leq \phi_l^{12u}, \quad \epsilon_{21} \geq \phi_l^{21u}, \quad \epsilon_{22} \leq \phi_l^{21u}, \quad (10)$$

$$\epsilon_{11} - \epsilon_{12} \leq P_x, \quad \epsilon_{21} - \epsilon_{22} \leq P_x, \quad (11)$$

The lower and upper bounds of the power levels received by transceivers in Hub1 and Hub2 are calculated by constraints (10). Constraint (11) ensures that the difference between the highest and lowest SC power levels does not exceed the threshold defined for transceivers placed at the hub nodes. Note that nonlinearity increases with the number of channels (total power in the fiber). The rest of the constraints are used to ensure that the power per SC does not exceed the preset nonlinear power threshold in critical points across the horseshoe in worst-cases.

$$\begin{aligned} & - \sum_a A_a M_d^{l,a} - \sum_{lx} \gamma_{lx,12}^{exp} N_d^{l,lx} - \gamma_{l,12}^{exp} + \sum_z p_{12,z}^{hub} P_z + \\ & \sum_g \mu_g^{b_1} G_g + \sum_a \sum_g \mu_{a,g}^{12} G_g M_d^{l,a} \leq P_n \quad \forall l \in L \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & - \sum_a A_a M_u^{l,a} - \sum_{lx} \gamma_{lx,21}^{exp} N_u^{l,lx} - \gamma_{l,21}^{exp} + \sum_z p_{21,z}^{hub} P_z + \\ & \sum_g \mu_g^{b_2} G_g + \sum_a \sum_g \mu_{a,g}^{21} G_g M_u^{l,a} \leq P_n \quad \forall l \in L \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Constraints (12) and (13) prevent the signal power from exceeding a predefined limit for downstream transmission.

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_z p_{l,12,z}^{leaf} P_z + \sum_g \mu_{l_n,g}^{u_1} G_g + \sum_{a,g} \mu_{a,g}^{12} G_g (M_u^{l_n,a} - M_u^{l_m,a}) \\ & - \sum_a A_a (M_u^{l_n,a} - M_u^{l_m,a}) - \sum_{lx} \gamma_{lx,12}^{exp} (N_u^{l_n,lx} - N_u^{l_m,lx}) - \\ & - \gamma_{l,12}^{add/drop} \leq P_n \quad \forall l_m \in L, l_n \in L, l_m \geq l_n \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_z p_{l,21,z}^{leaf} P_z + \sum_g \mu_{l_n,g}^{u_2} G_g + \sum_{a,g} \mu_{a,g}^{21} G_g (M_d^{l_n,a} - M_d^{l_m,a}) \\ & - \sum_a A_a (M_d^{l_n,a} - M_d^{l_m,a}) - \sum_{lx} \gamma_{lx,21}^{exp} (N_d^{l_n,lx} - N_d^{l_m,lx}) - \\ & - \gamma_{l,21}^{add/drop} \leq P_n \quad \forall l_m \in L, l_n \in L, l_m \geq l_n \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Constraints (14) and (15) guarantee that the power of each SC does not exceed the established threshold for upstream signals after passing through each leaf node in the horseshoe network.

$$\sum_g \mu_g^{b_1} G_g + \sum_z p_{12,z}^{hub} P_z \leq P_n \quad (16)$$

$$\sum_g \mu_g^{b_1} G_g + \sum_z p_{21,z}^{hub} P_z \leq P_n \quad (17)$$

Constraints (16) and (17) ensure the output power of booster amplifiers stays within the range that guarantees linear or quasi-linear operation when considering transmission over the optical fiber.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, we evaluate the advantage of the launch power control in metro-aggregation filterless horseshoe networks with P2MP transceivers when using the proposed optimization framework. Dual-polarization 16-QAM modulation is assumed, and a minimum receiver input power of $P_s = -24$ dBm per SC is set for both low and high data rate transceivers. The launch power of transceivers has a minimum value of -21 dBm per SC and a maximum value of -12 dBm per SC with increments of 1 dBm between these two values [14]. To

minimize penalties induced by nonlinear interference during fiber transmission, the maximum allowable power at the input of any fiber link is set to $P_n = -8$ dBm per SC. We assume that all links are comprised of single-mode fibers exhibiting a loss coefficient of 0.22 dB/km. Each Erbium-doped Fiber Amplifier (EDFA) can have a gain between 6 dB and 20 dB, with 1 dB increments.

Four scenarios are considered for the power splitting ratios of the passive couplers.

- Scenario 1: Balanced 50/50 couplers are used.
- Scenario 2: Only couplers with a 20/80 ratio (20% drop and add ratios, and 80% for express) are available.
- Scenario 3: Only 30/70 and 10/90 couplers.
- Scenario 3: All ratios from 10% to 90% with steps of 10% are available.

The optimization framework, detailed in Section III, is implemented using Julia programming. Specifically, the JuMP package is used because of its high-level and efficient environment suitable for such problems [15]. The CPLEX solver is used to solve all optimization instances.

Figure 3 presents the average number of amplifiers required during the optimization of 10 horseshoe networks, and the average SC power difference for the transceivers in both hubs in these network instances. Results are shown when considering two cases regarding the transmitter launch power level of each transceiver: fixed to the maximum value or variable according to the range previously defined. As can be seen in Figs. 3 (a) and (c), the variable launch power offers a significant advantage in both the baseline and extended horseshoe network topologies compared to the use of transceivers with fixed maximum launch power in all coupler configurations. This flexibility allows for a reduction in the number of amplifiers required. Importantly, with perfectly balanced 50/50 couplers, there is no room for optimization through coupler ratio adjustments. In this specific case, variable launch power control provides the greatest benefit by introducing an additional degree of freedom. By optimally adjusting the launch power, the number of amplifiers can be reduced by almost 25%. When the total length of the horseshoe increases from around 110km (baseline) to 220km (extended), approximately two additional amplifiers will be required.

For optimal transceiver performance, the SCs power difference should be minimized. While a difference less than 10 dB may not cause noticeable degradation [7], aiming for smaller values provides a margin and helps ensure reliable design and operation. Similar to the reduction in amplifier count (our primary objective), Figure 3(b) and (d) demonstrate a significant decrease in the average power difference between SCs for both the baseline and extended horseshoe configurations when launch power control is enabled. On average, the power difference between SCs tends to be slightly lower for extended horseshoe configurations. This phenomenon can be attributed to the fact that these topologies demand a larger number of optical amplifiers, which combined with the capability of adjusting the transmitters' launch power results in more

flexibility to equalize the power levels of the SCs that reach the hub nodes.

While we have demonstrated the advantages of launch power control in both baseline and extended horseshoe topology, the relationship between the control range and these benefits should also be examined. To explore this, we conducted a simulation series comparing two extreme coupler scenarios: "50/50" and "All" for only extended horseshoes. In our terminology, a 0 dB launch power control range signifies a fixed maximum launch power. Conversely, as the control range increases, the launch power can be adjusted within a wider range. For example, a 1 dB control range allows for launch power values of -12 dBm and -13 dBm, whereas a 4 dB control range corresponds for launch power figures between -12 dBm and -16 dBm. Figure 4 shows how the number of optical amplifiers and the SCs power difference evolve as launch power control increases from 0 dB up to 9 dB in steps of 1 dB. Noteworthy, in both the "50/50" and "All" scenarios, most of the amplifier reduction is achieved with a launch power control range of only 4 dB. However, the reduction in SCs power difference improves continuously with increasing the launch power control range. It is important to note that the observed fluctuations in SCs power difference are likely because it is not a primary objective and is always constrained to the set of feasible solutions that minimize the total number of optical amplifiers. Hence, the SCs power difference might even slightly increase, as seen in the plots.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper has described a comprehensive framework to optimize the design of filterless horseshoe metro-aggregation networks using P2MP transceivers while leveraging transmitter launch power control. The results obtained on a set of network topologies generated according to the statistical distribution of real and fabricated metro-aggregation networks highlight the benefits of employing launch power control for digital SCs power equalization in filterless optical networks. In particular, the number of optical amplifiers required can be reduced, and the maximum power difference between SCs reaching the same hub receiver can also be reduced. This results in a more cost-effective and robust network deployment and operation.

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Fig. 3. (a,c) Optimized average total number of amplifiers versus coupler ratio scenarios, and (b,d) average SCs power difference at hubs for the baselines and extended horseshoes .

Fig. 4. (a) Average number of amplifiers and (b) SCs power difference for Extended horseshoes and "50/50" and "All" ratios versus the launch power range.

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